

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

IMPACT OF DIABETES MELLITUS ON COGNITIVE DELAY AMONG PATIENTS WITH ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE, VASCULAR AND MIXED DEMENTIA

Valkova M.
PhD, MD

Neurology Clinic, University Hospital "Sofamed", Bulgaria

Abstract

Aim of the study: to examine the additional effect of diabetes mellitus (DM) on cognitive delay of patients with Alzheimer's disease (AD), Vascular dementia (VD) and mixed dementia (MD).

Material and methods: We examined 45 elderly patients with DM (9 AD, 21 VD and 15 MD) and 101 patients without DM (38 AD, 56 VD and 37 MD) twice with the following neuropsychological battery: Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), Isaack's Set Test (IST), Literal Fluency Test (LFT), 10 words memory test (10WMT), Clock Drawing Test (CDT), Digit Span Test (DST), Digit Symbol Substitution Test (DSST), Hamilton Depression Scale (HDS).

Results: DM was associated with additional MMSE scoring decrease in MD, IST delay among AD and MD, recognition decrease among VD and MD and DST forward impairment forward among AD. We found additional decrease on DSST scoring and delayed recall and increasing of HDS at all groups.

Conclusions: DM could cause mild additional cognitive deterioration and might increase the severity of depression in patients with AD, VD and MD even for the short period of time. The most affected cognitive domains are delayed recall, recognition and complex attention.

Keywords: diabetes mellitus, cognitive impairment, dementia.

Introduction: Alzheimer's disease (AD) and vascular dementia (VD) are the leading causes of dementia all over the world (Cao, 2020). They frequently coexist among elderly patients, known as mixed dementia (MD) (Custodio, 2017). Vascular risk factors and metabolic syndrome are strongly associated with both AD and VD (Qureshi, 2025). Diabetes mellitus type 2 (DM) is a significant risk factor for late onset AD, VD and MD (Custodio, 2017; Qureshi, 2025; Lemche 2025). Moreover, it is very frequent in adults with or without developed dementia (Sakib, 2023; Nagasawa, 2024; Sola, 2024). However, there is very few data on influence of DM on cognitive delay in cases with already developed cognitive impairments and dementia.

The objective of the study: The aim of our study was to examine the influence of DM on cognitive delay of patients with AD, VD and MD.

Material and Methods:

We examined 45 patients with DM (on the average age of 75.4 ± 6.99 years, 15 males and 30 females, of them 9 with AD, 21 with VD and 15 with MD) and 101 patients without DM (on the average age of 77.29 ± 7.63 years, 33 males and 68 females, of them 38 patients with AD, 56 with VD and 37 with MD).

The inclusion criteria for patients were (1) age 50-90 years; (2) The existence of AD or VD or MD, proved clinically, laboratory and with imaging (magnetic – resonance technique). Lack of space occupying brain process, brain operation, stroke. Lack of anamnesis for idiopathic or symptomatic epilepsy, brain injury or other brain diseases, different from AD or VD; (3) For patients with AD – only classical amnesic type of the disease. All patients with atypical phenotype were excluded.; (4) For patients with VD – we include only those with small vessels disease; MD patients should

have degeneration due to AD+ small vessels disease only. (5) Existence of cognitive deficit at ≥ 2 cognitive domains at the beginning of the study and MMSE scoring between 18 and 25 points; (6) Lack of severe anxiety or moderate to severe depression and lack of history for mayor depression episode, mania, bipolar disorder or schizophrenia; (7) No use of psychoactive substances – alcohol, benzodiazepines, antipsychotics, antiepileptic drugs, opioids or prohibited substances; (8) Lack of decompensated somatic diseases; (9) Free willing to be included in the study and signed written inform consent.

Methods:

After clinical interview, proven of diagnosis on the basis of history of the disease, neuropsychological examination, laboratory and imaging data, the patients were included into the study.

They were examined twice – at the beginning of the study and two years after it.

The neuropsychological battery used included Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), Isaack's Set Test (for semanticfluency), Literal Fluency Test (LFT, Bulgarian version type H-O-M-A, 1 minute for every letter) for phonemic fluency, 10 words memory test (10WMT, Bulgarian version), Clock Drawing Test (CDT), Digit Span Test (DST), 90 sec Digit Symbol Substitution Test (DSST), 21 Hamilton Depression Scale (HDS) and Spielberger-Hanin Anxiety Scale (SHAS). Patients with $21HDS \geq 15$ points and those with $SHAS \geq 2.5$ points were excluded.

For statistical analysis we used SPSS 20. ANOVA, MANOVA and paired T-tests and nonparametric tests for small samples were used. All results were interpreted at 95 confidential level (p 0.05).

Results:

1. Demographics. The demographic data is presented at table 1. Our samples were statistically comparable. There were no statistically significant differences by gender, age or formal education between DM and non DM groups. DM and nonDM patients had similar other vascular risk factors such as arterial hypertension, arterial fibrillation, ischemic heart disease and carotid atherosclerosis ($p > 0.05$).

2. The impact of DM on cognitive delay.

DM was associated with additional cognitive impairments (additional cognitive delay) in all our patients (see table 2). However, there were no associations between DM and additional delays on some cognitive scales (LFT, Immediate recall, DST forward and CDT).

During our short period (2 years) we failed to find any association between MMSE decline and DM at overall group of our patients, AD group and VD group. But patients with MD showed bigger decrease of MMSE scoring in association with DM.

DM negatively impact the IST performance of patients with AD and MD, but not of those with VD.

We found statistically significant association between DM and decrease of DR performances of all patients but it was most prominent in cases with VD, followed by those with MD.

DM was associated with the delay of DST backward scoring only at the group of AD patients. However, patients with DM showed significantly more prominent deterioration in DSST scoring than those without.

Discussion:

The coexistence of dementia and diabetes is very high (Michailidis, 2022). In our relatively small cohort of 146 patients, DM was found in 30%. The association between dementia and DM is complex and includes coexistence of other vascular risk factors and engagement in atherosclerotic cascade, insulin resistance at important brain regions and decreased cleaning of amyloid (Chen, 2022). We failed to find any significant additional deterioration on overall cognitive performance, measured by MMSE, associated with DM in our patients with VD and AD. Lack of statistically significant correlation between DM and performances on screening tools for Cognitive impairments incl. MMSE was found from other authors (Li J, 2017). The explanation of this finding should be searched in the complex influences of factors such as development of additional compensatory mechanisms from diabetic brain, positive role of antidiabetic treatment on cognition and relatively slow deterioration of performances on these tests during the time of the follow up (Li J, 2017; Lei H, 2022). However, we found statistically significant additional deterioration on MMSE due to DM among patients with MD. The link between DM and cognitive delay of MD patients is unclear, but according to us it might be due to additionally impaired compensatory mechanisms of the brain, more aggressive course of dementia and the synergetic effects of other vascular factors in this group.

Although DM is not associated with additional delay of overall cognitive functioning in most of our patients, it is associated with more prominent decrease in

some cognitive domains such as memory and executive functions.

We found additional DM associated deterioration of semantic, but not phonemic verbal fluency (VF) among patients with AD and MD, and no effect on those with pure VD. VF is defined as a cognitive function that “facilitates information retrieval from memory. It engages executive control and other cognitive processes, such as selective attention, selective inhibition, mental set shifting, internal response generation, and self-monitoring, as well as imagination and psychomotor skills” (Gierach, 2022). According to Reyes Bueno et al. (2024) patients with amnesic mild cognitive impairment and DM showed low results on VF tests vs those with mild nonamnesic cognitive impairment or those with amnesic cognitive impairment without DM, although the exact cause of such differences is unclear. The lack of DM effect on deterioration of VF in cases with VD was obtained. Sola et al. (2024) found only small effects of DM on phonemic VF and no effects on semantic one in community dowedled studies and studies on vascular cognitive impairment but not AD (Sola, 2024). Such findings are consistent with ours. And although it is well known that the development of small vessel disease is associated with DM and that it plays important role for VF impairment (Sola, 2024), DM patients with already developed vascular cognitive impairments might elaborate some specific compensatory mechanisms or other vascular and nonvascular factors might play more important role than DM itself.

We failed to find any association between DM and additional deterioration of working memory (measured by immediate recall and DST forward), results similar to those obtained from other studies (Reyes Bueno, 2024; Sola, 2024). But we found statistically significant (although mild) DM associated deterioration of complex attention (measured by DSST) among all groups. This was more prominent in cases with VD. Complex attention as a process that requires good white matter integration and connectivity. Prediabetes and DM causes microstructural abnormalities in white matter, leading to white matter disintegration and disconnection (Jing, 2022). These microstructural changes increase over time. We hypothesized that DM has synergetic with other vascular risk factors effect on white matter changes, which are most prominent in VD. On the other hand, patients with amnesic AD type with or without DM already have deficits of complex attention at the beginning of cognitive complains (Cummings, 2024) so the additional deterioration due to DM is not so obvious in these cases, but exists. AD patients with DM show mild additional deterioration of focused attention than those with AD but without DM. We found statistically significant effect of DM on the decrease of delayed recall (DR) among patients with AD, VD and MD. The results from previous studies are inconsistent. According to Nagasawa et al. (2024), DM is associated with DR impairment in elderly. Sakib et al. (2023) found significant association between DR decline and DM, more prominent among elderly than middle – aged patients. However other studies found no or negligible impact of DM on this cognitive domain (Sola, 2024).

We hypothesized that DM might play age related impact on DR in cases with dementia. Most of our patients (except those with AD) also showed mild but significant DM associated decrease of recognition, which is a marker of episodic memory, which may be due to the impact of DM on hippocampal volume and functions (Zhang, 2022).

DM impact the severity of depression in our patients, which also play important role for cognitive performances. The associations between DM, cognitive impairment and depression are found from other authors (Reyes Bueno, 2024; Sola, 2024, Khan, 2025) and are due to functional and structural changes of diabetic brain (Zhang, 2022; Khan, 2025). Such negative triad should be taken into account from the society and medical and social services. Khan et al. (2025) proposed “the integration of routine mental health screening for high-risk elderly T2DM patients and the development of comprehensive diabetes management programs that address both physical and mental health aspects”.

Conclusions: DM could cause mild additional cognitive deterioration and might increase the severity of depression in patients with AD, VD and MD even for the short period of time. The most affected cognitive domains are delayed recall, recognition and complex attention.

Limitations of the study.

The first limitation of our study is associated with the relatively small samples conducted in it. The second limitation is due to the duration of follow up which is relatively short so our study represents only the short time effects of DM on cognitive domains and depression.

We propose more wide studies on DM associated deterioration of cognitive functions among patients with already developed cognitive impairment and dementia. Such studies could give responses to very important questions concerning the management of elderly patients with dementia, depression and DM and the exact needs of the social and medical systems that take care for such patients.

Table 1.

Demographics.							
	AD n=	VD n=	MD n=	Total n=	Age	Male: female Ratio	Formal education (basic: middle: high)
Patients without DM	29	35	37	101 (69.18%)	77.29±7.63	33:68	6:58:37
Patients with DM	9	21	15	45 (30.82%)	75.4±6.99	15:30	6:25:14
Total	38	56	52	146 (100%)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05

Legend DM diabetes mellitus; AD – Alzheimer’s disease; VD – Vascular dementia; MD – Mixed dementia
Age – the exact age of patient at the period of inclusion into the study in years.

Table 2.

The Additional effect of diabetes mellitus on the deterioration on cognitive performances.				
The impact of DM on additional deterioration of:	All patients	AD	VD	MD
MMSE (p.)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05	p=0.0062
IST (p.)	p>0.05	p=0.0419	p>0.05	p=0.0456
LFT (p.)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05
10WMT				
Immediate recall (words)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05
Delayed recall (words)	p=0.0235	p=0.0451	p=0.0051	p=0.0275
Recognition (words)	p=0.0058	p>0.05	p=0.0032	p=0.0275
DST forward (p.)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05
DST backward (p.)	p>0.05	p=0.0415	p>0.05	p>0.05
DSST (p.)	p=0.0359	p=0.0368	p=0.0051	p=0.0409
CDT (p.)	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05	p>0.05
21HDS increasing (p.)	p=0.0136	p=0.0098	p=0.0245	p=0.0129

References

1. Cao Q, Tan CC, Xu W, Hu H, Cao XP, Dong Q et al. The Prevalence of Dementia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. J Alzheimers Dis. 2020;73(3):1157-1166.

2. Chen W, Cai W, Hoover B, Kahn CR. Insulin action in the brain: cell types, circuits, and diseases. Trends Neurosci. 2022 May;45(5):384-400.

3. Custodio N, Montesinos R, Lira D, Herrera-Pérez E, Bardales Y, Valeriano-Lorenzo L. Mixed dementia: A review of the evidence. *Dement Neuropsychol*. 2017 Oct-Dec;11(4):364-370.
4. Cummings J, Osse AML, Cammann D, Powell J, Chen J. Anti-Amyloid Monoclonal Antibodies for the Treatment of Alzheimer's Disease. *BioDrugs*. 2024 Jan;38(1):5-22
5. Gierach M, Rasmus A, Orłowska E. Verbal Fluency in Metabolic Syndrome. *Brain Sci*. 2022 Feb 12;12(2):255.
6. Jing J, Zhou Y, Pan Y, Cai X, Zhu W, Zhang Z et al. Reduced white matter microstructural integrity in prediabetes and diabetes: A population-based study. *EBioMedicine*. 2022 Aug;82:104144.
7. Qureshi D, Allen NE, Kuźma E, Littlejohns TJ. Metabolic syndrome and risk of incident all-cause dementia, Alzheimer's disease and vascular dementia: a systematic review and meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. *Alzheimers Res Ther*. 2025 Aug 23;17(1):198.
8. Khan F, Hussain S, Singh S, Sawlani KK, Usman K, Sachan AK et al. A Cross-Sectional Study on the Prevalence and Predictors of Cognitive Impairment and Depression in Elderly Patients With Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Cureus*. 2025 Jan 21;17(1):e77753.
9. Lemche E, Hortobágyi T, Kiecker C, Turheimer F. Neuropathological links between T2DM and LOAD: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Physiol Rev*. 2025 Jul 1;105(3):1429-1486.
10. Lei H, Hu R, Luo G, Yang T, Shen H, Deng H et al. Altered Structural and Functional MRI Connectivity in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Related Cognitive Impairment: A Review. *Front Hum Neurosci*. 2022 Jan 6;15:755017.
11. Li J, Cesari M, Liu F, Dong B, Vellas B. Effects of Diabetes Mellitus on Cognitive Decline in Patients with Alzheimer Disease: A Systematic Review. *Can J Diabetes*. 2017 Feb;41(1):114-119.
12. Michailidis M, Moraitou D, Tata DA, Kallinderi K, Papamitsou T, Papaliagkas V. Alzheimer's Disease as Type 3 Diabetes: Common Pathophysiological Mechanisms between Alzheimer's Disease and Type 2 Diabetes. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2022 Feb 28;23(5):2687.
13. Nagasawa K, Matsumura K, Uchida T, Suzuki Y, Nishimura A, Okubo M et al. Global cognition and executive functions of older adults with type 1 diabetes mellitus without dementia. *J Diabetes Investig*. 2024 Jul;15(7):922-930.
14. Reyes Bueno JA, Sánchez-Guijo G, Ráez PD, García-Arnés JA, Garzón-Maldonado FJ, Castro VS et al. Effects of Type 2 Diabetes on the Neuropsychological Profile in Mild Cognitive Impairment. *J Alzheimers Dis*. 2024;99(3):887-897.
15. Sakib MN, Ramezan R, Hall PA. Diabetes status and cognitive function in middle-aged and older adults in the Canadian longitudinal study on aging. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*. 2023 Dec 1;14:1293988.
16. Sola T, Sola FM, Jehkonen M. The Effects of Type 2 Diabetes on Cognitive Performance: A Review of Reviews. *Int J Behav Med*. 2024 Dec;31(6):944-958.
17. Zhang T, Shaw M, Cherbuin N. Association between Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus and Brain Atrophy: A Meta-Analysis. *Diabetes Metab J*. 2022 Sep;46(5):781-802.